

Figure S5 : Contrasting OTUs across development

A. Abundance fold changes across development. Contrasting OTUs were identified by filtering OTUs with an abundance of at least 100 reads across 20% of sample and using DESeq2 with a significance cutoff of 0.01. B. Heatmap representation of contrasting OTUs abundances across development. The heatmap was produced using a principal component analysis based on unifracs distances.